

Sensorless monitoring of induction motor temperature with an online estimation of stator and rotor resistances taking the effect of machine parameters variation into account

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Abstract: A novel and accurate method for induction motor online temperature monitoring based stator and rotor resistances thermal variation using Arduino-Matlab Simulink technique is proposed and implemented in this paper. Estimation of stator resistance as an indicator of stator winding and rotor bars temperature. Obtaining an accurate determination of stator and rotor resistances is very important for this approach.

A new determination of stator and rotor resistances for purpose of motor temperature monitoring in steady-state operation is proposed based on the motor dynamic model in a rotating reference frame. In this model, the effect of iron core losses is taken as a reflection of iron core resistance as a voltage drop in the stator and rotor circuits. The skin and skew effect in the rotor circuit, stray load loss in stator and rotor circuits, variation effect in the magnetizing inductance, variation in stator and rotor resistances are taken in this model to obtain an accurate temperature on line monitoring. An experimental result on the line connected induction motor satisfied the validity of the proposed model of analysis and method of motor temperature monitoring.

Keywords: temperature monitoring, stator, and rotor resistance estimation, dynamic model, iron core loss, stray loss, skin-effect, skew effect.

1- Introduction:

Many failure resources of induction motors are caused by a breakdown of a stator winding insulation due to thermal overloading. Therefore to extend the life of insulation, the temperature of stator winding must be online monitored and protect the motor under thermal overloading [1-2].

Because of the difficulty and high cost of installing thermal sensors inside the machine, the protection against thermal depends on fuses, thermal overload relays, and electronic-overload relays, which has a low cost for many years. Recently, temperature estimation using microcontrollers with thermal models became available to compensate for the shortcoming of overload relays [3]. Thermal models for temperature determination provide high accuracy than that of overload relays but cannot respond to the change in motor thermal characteristics. The assumed fixed machine variables in the thermal model cannot respond to the temperature rise in case of abnormal conditions, such as a failure in the cooling system leading to a rapid motor failure.

The motor temperature estimators can be divided into two categories:

- 1- Off-line estimation: the variables of the induction machine are calculated off-line by no-load test, blocked-rotor test, and load test. These methods are called variables identification methods.
- 2- On-line estimation: the motor variables are calculated during the conventional operation of the machine.

The off-line temperature estimation models give poor accuracy due to the machine parameters are considered constant, while the online estimators give more accurate results than the off-line estimators due to the effect of temperature variation on the determination of stator and rotor resistance is considered. In online temperature calculation methods there are five types of stator and rotor resistances estimation:

- 1- Zero sequence model by solving a least-squares minimization problem [4]. This technique achieves the machine parameters variation concerning zero sequence quantities.

- 2- DC injection model, which is simply realizable for on-line connected induction motor, but this model suffers from harmonic generation, which appears as torque pulsation ripple on, the motor shaft [2].
- 3- 'Model Reference adaptive system (MRAS) estimators'. These estimators are proposed in [5-8]. The main drawback of these algorithms is that the high-performance hardware to calculate the values of stator and rotor resistances, due to the need to solve complex non-linear equations, as well as the variation in motor parameters is not considered in these models.
- 4- Hybrid model based on the fixed thermal model for less than 50% of a motor nominal load and machine parameters identification model for greater than 50% of motor nominal load to estimate the motor temperature [9]. This hybrid model cannot respond to the temperature rise in case of a failure in the cooling system, which leads to a rapid failure of the machine. Also, the parameters identification model ignores all the machine variable parameters such as magnetizing saturation, skin effect, and skew factor.
- 5- Induction machine dynamic model. This method does not require any external injection. It depends on motor parameters estimation, which is not linear and depends on operating conditions [10-15].

In [10] the rotor resistance estimation is based on a machine dynamic model and artificial neural network, considering the effect of skin (slip frequency). In [11] the rotor temperature estimation, based on the dynamic model of the machine and indirect flux oriented control algorithm. In [12] thermal monitoring of induction motor in on-line steady-state operation base on an estimation of rotor resistance the dynamic electrical model, while the rotor speed is calculated from the dynamic mechanical model of the motor. In this model, the magnetizing saturation, iron-core loss, stray-load loss, skin effect, and skew-factor are omitted. In [13] an online estimation motor is presented taking the effect of temperature variation. The magnetizing inductance is constant. The iron-core loss, stray-load loss, skin-effect, and skew-factor are also omitted in this model.

In [14] calculation of stator resistance, and rotor resistance is based on the computation of D-axis rotor flux linkage (λ_{dr}) in equation (19) of the model. Since the equation is wrong, the author attributes the poor accuracy and high error rate in calculating the stator resistance to the error rate in the determination of the rotor resistance, especially at very high speed (high frequency) of the motor because the calculation of the stator resistance depends on the calculation of the rotor resistance. The fact is that the calculation of the rotor resistance depends on the value of the magnetizing inductance, which is low at high speed after the motor reaches the state of magnetic saturation. The author believes that a high sensitivity in calculating stator resistance is caused by errors in calculating rotor resistance, magnetizing inductance, and leakage magnetic inductances. Also, there is an error in estimating the magnetic flux linkage of the stator and rotor which is amplified due to the high frequency of the source (high speed of the motor), as well as the presence of an error rate in the measurement of the source voltage, line current, and motor speed, as the resistors calculations depend on these variables directly. This leads to the inability to correct estimation and monitor the motor temperature. The fact that the main reason for a high error in calculating stator and rotor resistance is neglecting the effect of magnetic saturation in calculating the magnetic inductance, as well as neglecting the skin and skew effect in calculating the rotor resistance. Also neglecting the effect of stray losses in the motor in addition to the error in equation (19) caused to have a high error rate in the calculation of the resistors and the estimation of the motor temperature.

In [15] indeed considering the magnetic inductance to be constant during the operation of the motor leads to a certain error in estimating the resistances of the stator and rotor, but the author attributes the high error rate in the calculations to the constant magnetic and this is incorrect because the very high error rate is caused by an error in the equations of the dynamic model of the machine, especially equations (3, 4, 25) in that dynamic model. As the researcher used equation (3, 4) in his research to obtain a mathematical equation to calculate the rotor resistance from equation (14), and due to the error in equations (3, 4), the equation for calculating the rotor resistance (14) is incorrect. This is evident from Fig. (1) in that reference, where the error rate reached

150% in calculating the error resistance. The other mistake is the use of equations (14-16) in calculating the resistance of the stator from Fig. (3).

For sensor-less temperature monitoring in the steady-state online operation of the induction motor, a new dynamical model of the machine is proposed. The model is considered in a synchronously rotating reference frame, taking all the machine parameters variation into account. The iron core temperatures effect, the stray load loss temperature effect, magnetizing inductance saturation, skin effect, and the skew effect are considered as variable parameters. The rotor speed can be estimated from the dynamic mechanical model or can be measured online by measuring supply frequency, phase, and phase current. The measured parameters can be fed to the Arduino controller with the computer Matlab Simulink to estimate the stator and rotor resistances and stator and rotor temperature variation online during the steady-state operation of the motor.

2- Determination of Stator and Rotor Resistances Based on Dynamic Model:

In [14, 15] it is confirmed that the dynamic model of the induction motor used in estimating the resistance of the stator and rotor cannot be used and this is due to the difficulty in obtaining acceptable accuracy in calculating stator and rotor resistance. This is confirmed by all references (researches) in this field through practical experiments, and there are no reasons that can be mentioned to diagnose the poor accuracy of the results obtained.

I believe that the main reason for the poor accuracy of the estimated results of stator and rotor resistances from the dynamic model is the use of all variables in the model as constants. This is not correct because the machine variables are varied during the machine operation and this must be taken into account. In addition to that, neglecting many variables and not entering them within the model such as the effect of the skin phenomenon, skew, magnetic saturation, iron core losses, and stray losses.

Figure (1) Schematic diagram of the 3-phase induction motor-Arduino controller system

Figure (1) shows the schematic diagram of the 3-phase induction motor-Arduino controller system. The Arduino is connected online with the motor through ACS-712 type voltage and current sensors, while the motor is connected to the supply without interior temperature sensors.

In the current dynamic model shown in figure (2), all the motor parameters will be entered into the model to obtain high accuracy in calculating the stator and rotor resistances on which the machine temperature calculations depend directly. The following motor parameters can be considered in the dynamic model:

a-) Resistances of Stator and rotor - iron core:

The iron core resistance is varied with the temperature and air-gap voltage and can be calculated from the no-load test of the motor as [16]:

$$R_{ic} = V_g^2 / [K_T * (P_{nl} - I_o^2 * R_s)] \tag{1}$$

$$V_g = X_m * I_m = X_m * I_o * \sin(\phi_o) \tag{2}$$

$$I_m = \left[\frac{Q_{nl} - I_o^2 * X_{ls}}{X_m} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{3}$$

where V_g is the air-gap or magnetizing voltage per phase and can be calculated in terms of magnetizing reactance (X_m), no-load current (I_o) and no-load sine of power factor angle ($\sin(\phi_o)$). Also, the iron core resistance was obtained in terms of air-gap voltage from the no-

load test and curve-fitting technique as given in appendix-A.

$K_T=(1-D)$ is the temperature coefficient of the iron core loss.

D is the iron core power loss varying rate per $^{\circ}C$ and can be determined as [16]:

$$D = [P_{ic}(T_0) - P_{ic}(T)] / P_{ic}(T_0) \quad (4)$$

where $P_{ic}(T_0)$ is the power loss of iron core at ambient temperature and $P_{ic}(T)$ is the power loss iron core at any temperature. These iron core power losses can be measured from the no-load test of the motor.

$P_{n\ell}$ is the active no-load power loss per phase.

R_{s0} is the stator resistance per phase at ambient temperature.

$Q_{n\ell}$ is the reactive no-load power loss per phase.

$X_{\ell s}$ is the stator leakage reactance per phase.

The resistance (R_{ic}) of the iron core can be referred to on the stator and rotor circuits as a voltage drop to stay the dynamic model order fixed on 4th order while the effect of iron core loss is considered as shown in figure (1). The reflecting resistance on the stator circuit (R_{ssic}) and the reflecting resistance of iron core on the rotor circuit (R_{rsic}) calculated as [17]:

$$R_{ssic} = (R_{ic} * \omega_s * L_M) / [R_{ic}^2 + (\omega_s * L_M)^2] \quad (5)$$

$$R_{rsic} = s * R_{ssic} \quad (6)$$

Where R_{sic} is the iron core- resistance of the stator and calculated as:

$$R_{sic} = R_{ic} * (\omega_s * L_M)^2 / [R_{ic}^2 + (\omega_s * L_M)^2] \quad (7)$$

Where L_M is the magnetizing inductance per phase and can be obtained from the no-load test as:

$$L_M = X_m / \omega_s \quad (8)$$

$\omega_s = (2 * \pi * f)$ is the angular frequency in rad. / sec.

The modified magnetizing inductance (L_m) in figure (1) of the dynamic model can be calculated as:

$$L_m = L_M * R_{ic}^2 / [R_{ic}^2 + (\omega_s * L_M)^2] \quad (9)$$

b-) Stray load loss resistances:

The stray load loss resistances can be varied with the variation of stator and rotor resistances due to the temperature variation. These resistances can be calculated and introduced in the dynamic model as shown in figure (1). These resistances are derived in ref. [18] and given as series resistances in the stator and rotor circuits [18]:

$$R_{SS\ell} = (\omega_s * L_{\ell s})^2 * R_s / [R_s^2 + (\omega_s * L_{\ell s})^2] \quad (10)$$

$$R_{rSS\ell} = S^2 * (\omega_s * L'_{\ell r})^2 / R'_r \quad (11)$$

Where $R_{SS\ell}$ and $R_{rSS\ell}$ are stator and rotor series stray-load loss resistances respectively.

S is the motor slip and $L_{\ell r}$ is the rotor leakage inductance per phase.

c-) Include magnetizing saturation:

All induction machines operate in the saturation region and their characteristics are non-linear. The variation of magnetizing reactance (X_m) is the main factor in producing the magnetizing voltage (V_g).

The magnetizing voltage is the main factor in producing iron-core losses, rotor current, mechanical losses, and output power. The saturation reduces V_g and tends to increased. The saturation-effect is taken by the relation $X_m = f(I_m)$.

This function can be obtained experimentally from the no-load test by varying- supply voltage from 125% down to 25% of the rated value. Then the measurements of X_m and I_m can be interpolated by the curve-fitting technique [17] as given in appendix-A.

d-) Correction factors:

- i. The rotor phase leakage reactance can be corrected by the skew factor (K_{sq}) [19]:

$$\hat{X}_{\ell r} = \frac{X_m}{K_{sq}^2} (1 - K_{sq}^2) + \frac{\hat{X}_{\ell r}}{K_{sq}^2} \quad \text{total rotor leakage reactance} \quad (12)$$

$$K_{sq} = \sin\left(\frac{\pi * P_p}{Q_r}\right) / (\pi * P_p / Q_r) \quad \text{rotor skew factor} \quad (13)$$

Where P_p is the machine magnetic pole-pairs Q_r is the number of rotor slots (bars).

- ii. The rotor phase resistance can be corrected by the skew factor as :

$$\hat{R}_r = \check{R}_r / K_s^2 \tag{14}$$

- iii. The rotor phase resistance and leakage reactance can be corrected by the skin effect as [19] :

$$\hat{R}_r = \check{R}_r * [0.5 + 0.5 * \sqrt{S_r/S_m}] \tag{15}$$

$$\hat{X}_{\ell r} = \check{X}_{\ell r} * [0.4 + 0.6 * \sqrt{S_m/S_r}] \tag{16}$$

Where S_r is the rated machine slip and S_m is the machine slip at maximum torque and can be given as [19]:

$$S_m = \hat{R}_r / [(R_s + R_{ss\ell})^2 + (X_{\ell s} + \hat{X}_{\ell r})^2]^{1/2} \tag{17}$$

Also, the machine slip can be corrected due to the temperature effect as [20]:

$$\hat{S}_{r,m} = S_{r,m} * (T_r + K_a) / (T_{ref} + K_a) \tag{18}$$

where T_r is the rotor bar temperature at any load and T_{ref} is the temperature of insulation class level and can be obtained from the table of insulation class.

K_a is constant and equal to (225) for aluminum rotor bar type.

The dynamic electrical equations of the induction motor are derived from the proposed equivalent circuit shown in figure (2) as:

(a) D-axis equivalent circuit model

(b) Q-axis equivalent circuit model

Figure (2): D-Q axes modified equivalent-circuit of induction motor in the synchronously rotating frame.

$$v_{sd} = (R_s + R_{ss\ell}) i_{sd} + R_{ssic} i_{md} - \omega_s \psi_{sd} + \frac{d\psi_{sd}}{dt} \tag{19}$$

$$v_{sq} = (R_s + R_{ss\ell}) i_{sq} + R_{ssic} i_{mq} + \omega_s \psi_{sd} + \frac{d\psi_{sq}}{dt} \tag{20}$$

$$0 = (\hat{R}_r + R_{rssl}) i_{rd} + R_{rsic} i_{md} - \omega_{sl} \hat{\psi}_{rq} + \frac{d\hat{\psi}_{rd}}{dt} \tag{21}$$

$$0 = (\hat{R}_r + R_{rssl}) i_{rq} + R_{rsic} i_{mq} + \omega_{sl} \hat{\psi}_{rd} + \frac{d\hat{\psi}_{rq}}{dt} \tag{22}$$

Where $\omega_{sl} = \omega_s - \omega_r = s * \omega_s$ slip speed in electrical. radian / sec.

$\omega_r = P_p * \omega_m$ is the electrical angular speed of the motor in (electrical. radian/ sec.)

$\psi_{sd}, \psi_{sq}, \hat{\psi}_{rd}$ and $\hat{\psi}_{rq}$ are the stator and rotor flux linkage in D-Q axes respectively, and can be defined as :

$$\psi_{sd} = L_{\ell s} * i_{sd} + L_m * i_{md} \tag{23}$$

$$\psi_{sq} = L_{\ell s} * i_{sq} + L_m * i_{mq} \tag{24}$$

$$\hat{\psi}_{rd} = \hat{L}_{\ell r} * i_{rd} + L_m * i_{md} \tag{25}$$

$$\hat{\psi}_{rq} = \hat{L}_{\ell r} * i_{rq} + L_m * i_{mq} \tag{26}$$

Equations (19-22) can be transformed by making the D-axis rotating reference frame coincide and rotating synchronously with the D-axis stator current (i_{sd}). This makes the Q-axis stator current (i_{sq}) equal to zero ($i_{sq} = 0$). Then, by assuming steady-state operation condition, this leads to making the derivative of stator and rotor flux linkages in D-Q axes ($\frac{d\psi_{sd}}{dt}, \frac{d\psi_{sq}}{dt}, \frac{d\hat{\psi}_{rd}}{dt}, \frac{d\hat{\psi}_{rq}}{dt}$) equal to zero, and by substituting equations (23-26) in to (19-22) and further reduced to obtain the following equations :

$$v_{sd} = (R_s + R_{ss\ell} + R_{ssic}) i_{sd} + R_{ssic} * i_{rd} - \omega_s * L_m * i_{rq} \tag{27}$$

$$v_{sq} = \omega_s * (L_{\ell s} + L_m) * i_{sd} + \omega_s * L_m * i_{rd} \tag{28}$$

$$0 = R_{rsic} * i_{sd} + (\hat{R}_r + R_{rssl} + R_{rsic}) * i_{rd} + \omega_{sl} * (\hat{L}_{\ell r} + L_m) i_{rq} \tag{29}$$

$$0 = \omega_{sl} * L_m * i_{sd} + \omega_{sl} * (\hat{L}_{\ell r} + L_m) * i_{rd} + (\hat{R}_r + R_{rssl} + R_{rsic}) * i_{rq} \tag{30}$$

In equations (27-30), assuming $L_s = (L_{\ell s} + L_m)$ is the stator self-inductance and $L_r = (\hat{L}_{\ell r} + L_m)$ is the rotor self-inductance. Then solve these equations to get an expression for

stator phase resistance ($R_{S(t)}$) and rotor phase resistance ($\hat{R}_{r(t)}$) in terms of motor phase voltage, motor phase current, and rotor speed (ω_r) as:

$$\hat{R}_{r(t)} = \omega_{sl} * L_m * \left[\frac{\omega_s * L_r}{(\omega_s * L_s - i_{sd})} - \frac{L_r^2}{L_m^2} \right]^{1/2} - (R_{rssl} + R_{rsic}) \quad (31)$$

$$R_{S(t)} = \frac{v_{sd}}{i_{sd}} + \left[\frac{(\hat{R}_r + R_{rssl} + R_{rsic})}{(\omega_{sl} * L_r)} * \left(\frac{v_{sq}}{i_{sd}} - \omega_s * L_s \right) \right] - (R_{sssl} + R_{ssic}) \quad (32)$$

The rotor mechanical speed (ω_m) can be calculated from the dynamic mechanical model as :

$$\frac{d\omega_m}{dt} = \frac{1}{J} (T_e - T_\ell - V_f * \omega_m) \quad (33)$$

Where T_e is the electromagnetic torque of the motor and can be calculated as [21]:

$$T_e = \left(\frac{3}{2} \right) * P_p * L_m * (i_{sd} * i_{rq} - i_{sq} * i_{rd}) \quad (34)$$

T_ℓ is the motor load torque in (N . m).

J is the moment of inertia in ($K_g . m^2$).

P_p is the magnetic pole-pairs number.

V_f is the viscosity resistance factor N.m / (rad. / sec.) .

The magnetizing inductance (L_m) in terms of magnetizing current (I_m) from the no-load test can be introduced in the dynamic model as a polynomial curve fitting to take magnetizing saturation into account.

$i_{sq} = 0$, due to the D-axis reference frame coincide with the D-axis stator current (i_d).

i_{sd} is the measured phase current.

$$i_{rd} = (v_{sq} - \omega_s * L_s * i_{sd}) / (\omega_s * L_m) \quad (35)$$

$$i_{md} = i_{sd} + i_{rd} \quad (36)$$

$$i_{rq} = \frac{[-v_{sd} + (R_s + R_{sssl}) * i_{sd} + R_{ssic} * i_{md}]}{(\omega_s * L_m)} \quad (37)$$

$$i_{mq} = i_{sq} + i_{rq} \quad (38)$$

$$I_m = \sqrt{i_{md}^2 + i_{mq}^2} / \sqrt{2} \quad (39)$$

3- Sensorless online Monitoring of the motor winding temperature :

In the absence of temperature sensors, it is preferred to calculate the variation in the stator and rotor resistances during the normal steady-state operation of the machine, and then the stator and rotor winding temperature can be

calculated online at any load and operating time as [20]:

$$T_s = T_a + \frac{(R_{S(t)} - R_s)}{\alpha_s * R_s} \quad (40)$$

$$T_r = T_a + \frac{(\hat{R}_{r(t)} - R_r)}{\alpha_r * R_r} \quad (41)$$

Where $R_{r(t)}$ and $R_{S(t)}$ are the calculated rotor and stator resistance from equation (31-32).

R_r and R_s are the rotor and stator resistances at ambient temperature (25°C).

α_r and α_s are the temperature coefficients of the rotor and stator winding materials type ($\alpha_r = 0.004$, $\alpha_s = 0.0039$).

For comparison the results of this method, the stator and rotor winding temperature can be calculated at any online operating time from the following relations [20]:

$$T_s = \frac{I_s^2}{I_{sfl}^2} (T_{ref} - T_a) + T_a \quad (42)$$

$$T_r = \frac{(I_s - I_o)^2}{(I_{sfl} - I_o)^2} [T_{ref} - T_a] + T_a \quad (43)$$

Where I_s = stator current per phase at any load.

I_{sfl} = stator current per phase at full load from the nameplate of the machine.

I_o = stator no-load current per phase, from the no-load test of the machine.

T_{ref} = reference temperature depends on the class of insulation system(Appendix-B).

T_a = ambient temperature (25°C).

4- Result and Discussion:

The test bench consists of an induction 3-phase induction motor connected with an Arduino controller on a 3-phase AC supply, to estimate the motor stator winding and rotor bar temperature variation online without sensors during any operating time and load conditions. The motor specifications are given in appendix-A

The Arduino controller type UNO with voltage and current sensors type ACS 712.

The dynamic model of the motor is fed to the Arduino controller as a code (program) to calculate the rotor and then stator phase resistance and the temperature of stator winding and rotor bar can be estimated.

Figure (3) shows the online variation of stator winding and rotor bar resistances with time during the motor operation. The percentage variation of these resistances about 20% for the rotor bars and 12% for stator winding during 90 minutes of continuous motor operation. Figure (4) shows the variation of stator winding and rotor bar temperature with time during 90 minutes of continuous motor operation. The rotor bar temperature is about 10 °C above that of the stator coil temperature.

Figure (3): Resistance variation with time

Figure (4): Temperature variation with time

5-Conclusion:

A new and efficient method is proposed for accurate and sensor-less online monitoring of induction motor temperature during continuous operation in steady-state conditions. The accurate dynamic model of the induction motor is fed to the Arduino programmable controller as a code (program). The main parameters of calculation (phase voltage and current) are measured directly online by voltage and current sensors and then fed to the controller to

calculate online the rotor and stator phase resistances and their temperatures.

The error in estimating both rotor and stator resistances is minimized due to the flux saturation and skin effect are considered in the dynamic model. The iron core loss, stator copper loss, and rotor copper loss are considered heat sources.

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Appendix

- A-** The induction machine specification and parameters are given as :
 3-Phase, squirrel cage, Δ – *connected* , 220 V line voltage, 50 Hz, with the following parameters :
- $$P_{out} = 1500 W, N_s = 1500 r.p.m, I_f = 6.6 A, P_p = 2, \cos(\phi) = 0.8,$$
- $$R_s = 5.1 \Omega, \hat{R}_r = 3.5 \Omega, L_{\ell s} = 16 mH, \hat{L}_{\ell r} = 24 mH, L_M = 0.28 H,$$

$R_{ic} = 280 \Omega$ at rated voltage, $J = 0.025 \text{ Kg.m}^2$, $V_f = 0.002 \text{ N.m/(rad./sec.)}$
 Viscosity resistance factor, $R_{f\omega} = 1660 \Omega$,
 friction, and windage loss resistance, $T_{f\ell} = 10 \text{ N.m}$ full load torque, $I_0 = 1.0 \text{ A}$
 Design class-B, Insulation class-F, $K_T = 0.75$
 temperature coefficient of iron core loss, $\alpha_r = 0.004$ and $\alpha_s = 0.0039$ temperature
 coefficient of stator and rotor material type, the
 magnetizing inductance as a function of
 magnetizing current (I_m) is obtained as:
 $L_M = 0.0476 * I_m^5 - 0.513 * I_m^4 + 2.18 * I_m^3 - 4.57 * I_m^2 + 4.63 * I_m + 0.25$
 $R_{ic} = -0.0001985 * V_g^3 + 0.111 * V_g^2 - 23.11 * V_g + 840$

B- The table of insulation class level is given as [20] :

Insulation class level	Rated or reference temperature T_{ref} .(°C)
A	75
B	95
F	115
H	130

C- The table of design class is given as [20] :

Design class	$X_{\ell s}/\hat{X}_{\ell r}$ ratio
A, D, and wound rotor	1.0 ($X_{\ell s} = \hat{X}_{\ell r}$)
B	0.67 ($X_{\ell s} = 0.67 * \hat{X}_{\ell r}$)
C	0.43 ($X_{\ell s} = 0.43 * \hat{X}_{\ell r}$)